

Rate of Polymerisation of Silicic Acid and the Effect of Organic Solvents on it

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The gelation of silicic acid molecules in aqueous medium is a third-order condensation polymerisation process within the pH range 2.31 to 2.56. The time of gelation increases with the addition of organic solvents, viz., ethanol and glycol. A quantitative explanation has been furnished on the basis of formation of complex between silicic acid and organic solvents added.

Silicic acid sol sets to a gel by addition of electrolytes. Observations on the rate of gelation at different concentrations have been made by Merrill and Spencer¹, Hurd and Scheffer², Iler³, Ghosh and Sen⁴, and Alexander⁵. Hurd and Scheffer² report that at a constant temperature and between the pH range 4.8 and 6.5, the time required for the formation of gel varies inversely as the square of silica concentration. Alexander⁵, however, reports that between pH range of 1.7 and 2.1, the reaction is a third-order one, but at pH above 3.6, it can be best explained by a second-order reaction.

So far as the effect of organic solvents (hydrogen bonding agents) on the time of gelation of silicic acid sol is concerned, the data obtained by different authors show considerable disagreement. According to Hurd and Carver⁶, cane sugar and glycerol have practically no effect on the time of gelation, whereas ethanol, acetaldehyde, and acetone appreciably increase the time of gelation. It has been reported by Munro and Alves⁷ that the effect of non-electrolytes is gradually greater on the higher pH side of the minimum rate of gelation and is very little unless added in large quantities. Thus according to them, glycerol increases the time of gelation, which appears to be surprising to Hurd⁸ because of the dehydrating property of glycerol. Munro and Pearce⁹ found a regular increase in the time of gelation when higher members of a series of polyhydric alcohols were added to the sol mixtures. Prasad and Hattiangadi¹⁰ have reported acceleration of gel formation by alcohols added in small quantities on the higher and lower pH side of the minimum rate of gelation. But in highly acid medium or when added in large quantities in dilute acid medium, retardation of the gel formation have been observed by them.

1. *J. Phys. Coll. Chem.*, 1950, 54, 806.
2. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1941, 45, 588.
3. *Ibid.*, 1953, 57, 804.
4. *This Journal*, 1954, 31, 808.
5. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 2044.
6. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1933, 37, 321.
7. *Canad. J. Res.*, 1937, B15, 353.
8. *Chem. Rev.*, 1938, 22, 403.
9. *Canad. J. Res.*, 1938, B16, 390.
10. *This Journal*, 1929, 6, 653, 991; 1930, 7, 341.

It appears from what has been stated above, that there is some difference of opinion regarding the order of reaction in the pH range above 3.6 and the observations pertaining to the effect of organic solvents on the gelation of silicic acid sol. Besides, none of the authors, mentioned above, except Alexander, have worked with pure silicic acid sol. In consideration of these facts, a study of the effect of concentration of silica and that of organic solvents on the rate of gelation of pure silicic acid sol has been undertaken.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of the Silicic Acid.—The common method of preparation is the interaction of a solution of sodium silicate and an acid. Among the other processes of preparation, electrolysis of a solution of a silicate by Treadwell and Wieland¹¹, Kroger¹², and Bhatnagar and Mathur¹³, heating fine powder of Ottawa sand at 300-400° with water in a bomb by Lenher¹⁴, oxidation of silane with ozone by Kargin and Rabinovich¹⁵ may be cited. The use of ion-exchange resin for removal of sodium from sodium silicate has been first described by Bird¹⁶ and used thereafter by Walter¹⁷, Alexander³, and Mitra and Chari¹⁸, and others.

To obtain pure silicic acid we used ion-exchange method with sodium metasilicate ($\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$) of A.R. quality as the starting material. The silicate was dissolved in conductivity water and the solution filtered several times through quantitative Whatman filter papers (No. 42).

The resin used was Amberlite, IR-120 (H), analytical grade, of Rohm and Hass Company, Pennsylvania. To determine the exchange capacity of the resin it was titrated with NaOH solution, whence 15 g. of moist resin was found to exchange 30 ml. of *N*-NaOH normal solution. Having thus known the exchange capacity of the resin, a column was prepared on glass wool pad in a long pyrex tube. The length of the column was 20 cm. The resin in the column was washed several times with double distilled water until the percolated water attained the same conductance and pH as that of the water used. The sodium silicate solution was then percolated through the column at a slow rate, the amount (in ml) percolated being one-third of the total exchange capacity of the resin in order to get total conversion. A clear solution of silicic acid was thus obtained which was found free of sodium on analysis, thus indicating its purity.

Measurement of pH.—The pH of all the samples in an experiment was measured in a Cambridge Bench type pH meter.

Determination of Gel Point.—The silicic acid, prepared as above, set to a gel in course of time. The change from sol to gel state was followed by noting whether a small spherical

11. *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1900, 13, 842.

12. *Kolloid Z.*, 1922, 30, 16.

13. *Ibid.*, 1922, 30, 368.

14. *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1905, 53, 351.

15. *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1935, 31, 284.

16. National Aluminate Co., U. S. P. 2, 244, 325/1941.

17. E. T. du Pont de Nemours and Co., Inc., U. S. P. 2, 601, 352/1952.

18. *Symp. High Polymers, Calcutta*, 1960, 30-31, 17.

glass ball floated or sank, when gently placed on the surface of the sol. If the ball does not sink through the system but just floats on the surface, then the sol is assumed to have set. The reproducibility of this technique of determining the gel point is fairly satisfactory. In actual practice, the same experiment was repeated twice or thrice and the mean of the time taken to form gel was recorded.

For observing the effect of concentration, a concentrated sol was prepared and from it the other sols were obtained by dilution with conductivity water. The time of gelation was then determined by the floating-ball method.

Ethanol and glycol were used as the two organic solvents to observe their effect on the rate of gelation. In the case of the former, the loss due to evaporation, resulting from frequent opening of the cork of three test tubes for observation, was avoided by starting with three test tubes containing the same sol-solvent mixture, two of them being occasionally tested, the third one being tested at the proper time (an idea of the proper time can be gathered from the first two trial experiments). The starting time was recorded from the moment the sol was mixed with the organic solvent.

DISCUSSION

From the equigelation point of different samples containing the pure silicic acid at different concentrations, we have found out the order of the polymerisation reaction.

FIG. 1

Samples having different SiO_2 concentrations are found to vary in pH a little and within the short range of pH investigated, the acid molecules undergo condensation and the reaction is of the third order (Fig. 1). If the criteria, which have been developed for the formation of organic gels by Flory¹⁹ and Stockmayer²⁰ be applied to this case, the gel formation should take place at the stage when

$$p_c = \frac{1}{(f-1)}$$

where p_c is the critical value of p , which represents the ratio of the functional groups used up to the total number of functional groups initially present and ' f ' is the number of functional groups per molecule of silicic acid. Taking $f=4$, the gelation should start when 33% or more of the functional groups is consumed in the condensation process.

The observed order of the reaction may be accounted for by assuming

19. Flory, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **51**, 3334; 1940, **62**, 2261; 1941, **63**, 3083, 3091, 3096.

20. *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1943, **11**, 46; 1944, **12**, 125.

that two OH groups, one from each of two silicic acid molecules, react and another OH group of one of the reacting molecules or of a third molecule acts as a catalyst. Thus, the rate of reaction should be written as:

$$-\frac{dC}{dT} = k(\text{OH})^3 = kC^3 \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where k is the specific reaction velocity constant and C is the concentration of the reacting groups. It may be mentioned that in absence of an added catalyst, the esterification of a number of glycol by adipic acid has been found by Flory¹⁹ to be a reaction of the third order and has been interpreted in the manner discussed above.

The integrated form of the above third order reaction is

$$2 kt = \frac{1}{C^2} - \frac{1}{C_0^2} \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

where C is the concentration of the reacting groups at time t and C_0 is the initial concentration.

Since the critical value of p , i.e., p_c , is identical with the gel point (as stated previously), therefore at gel point, $C=C_0(1-p_c)$ and the equation (2) then becomes

$$\begin{aligned} t &= \frac{1}{2k} \left\{ \frac{1}{C_0^2(1-p_c)^2} - \frac{1}{C_0^2} \right\} \\ &= \frac{p_c(2-p_c)}{2k(1-p_c)^2} \cdot \frac{1}{C_0^2} \quad \dots \quad (3) \end{aligned}$$

or

$$\sqrt{t} = \left\{ \frac{p_c(2-p_c)}{2k(1-p_c)^2} \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}} \cdot \frac{1}{C_0} \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

Therefore a plot of $\sqrt{t}$ against $1/C_0$ will yield a straight line, the slope of which will determine

$$\left\{ \frac{p_c(2-p_c)}{2k(1-p_c)^2} \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

Since silicic acid molecule possesses four functional groups (OH groups), we may take the value of $p_c=1/3$ and k in term of the slope becomes

$$\frac{5}{8} \cdot \frac{1}{(\text{slope})^2}$$

The values of k obtained at 23°, 29°, and 31° are 1.70×10^{-4} , 6.24×10^{-4} , and 6.60×10^{-4} respectively. According to Iler³ and Alexander⁵, the fluoride ion present as an impurity in the system acts as a catalyst. To the present authors, however, the mechanism suggested above, appears to be more logical within the pH range investigated, viz., 2.31 and 2.56.

In our experiments, the time of gelation is found to increase continuously with the increase in the amount of ethanol or glycol added at a given concentration of SiO_2 at a constant temperature. The pH of the sol is also found to increase slightly with the addition of ethanol or glycol.

The square root of time of gelation, when plotted against molecular proportion of EtOH:H₂O, furnishes a straight line (Fig. 2, lines 1 to 3). This linear relationship may be accounted for in the following way:

FIG. 2

Ethanol and glycol retard the time of gelation of silicic acid. Let us consider the case of ethanol and assume that silicic acid forms complexes according to the equations:

The equilibrium constant

$$k_1 = \frac{[(\text{Complex})_1]}{[\text{H}_2\text{SiO}_3][\text{H}_2\text{O}]}$$

and

$$\text{The equilibrium constant } k_2 = \frac{[(\text{Complex})_2]}{[\text{H}_2\text{SiO}_3][\text{EtOH}]}$$

Let us next assume that the silicic acid-water complex alone forms gel. Therefore, when the system consisting of H₂SiO₃, EtOH, and H₂O attains equilibrium, it follows from equations (5) and (6), that

$$\frac{[(\text{Complex})_2]}{[(\text{Complex})_1]} = \frac{k_2}{k_1} \frac{[\text{EtOH}]}{[\text{H}_2\text{O}]}$$

$$\text{or} \quad [(\text{Complex})_2] = \frac{k_2}{k_1} \frac{[\text{EtOH}]}{[\text{H}_2\text{O}]} [(\text{Complex})_1] \quad (7)$$

It may be assumed that (Complex)₁ and (Complex)₂ together consume practically the whole of H₂SiO₃ taken. Therefore, we can write

$$\begin{aligned} [\text{H}_2\text{SiO}_3]_0 &= [(\text{Complex})_1] + [(\text{Complex})_2] \\ &= [(\text{Complex})_1] + \frac{k_2}{k_1} \frac{[\text{EtOH}]}{[\text{H}_2\text{O}]} [(\text{Complex})_1] \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{or,} \quad [(\text{Complex})_1] = [\text{H}_2\text{SiO}_3]_0 / \left\{ 1 + \frac{k_2}{k_1} \frac{[\text{EtOH}]}{[\text{H}_2\text{O}]} \right\} \quad (8)$$

Hence, concentration of H₂SiO₃ available for (Complex)₁ formation is .

$$[\text{H}_2\text{SiO}_3]_0 / \left\{ 1 + \frac{k_2}{k_1} \frac{[\text{EtOH}]}{[\text{H}_2\text{O}]} \right\} .$$

For the rate of gel formation we have,

$$t = \frac{1}{kC_0^2} \text{ (vide equation 3).}$$

According to our assumption (Complex)₁ is essential for gel formation. We therefore write 4 (Complex)₁ in place of C₀ and obtain for the rate of gel formation the following expression:

$$t = \frac{1}{k [4 (\text{Complex})_1]^2}$$

[Since (Complex)₁ is identified with Si(OH)₄ containing four functional groups].

Putting the value of (Complex)₁ from equation (8), the above expression becomes:

$$t = \frac{\left\{ 1 + \frac{k_2}{k_1} \frac{[\text{EtOH}]}{[\text{H}_2\text{O}]} \right\}^2}{16 k [\text{H}_2\text{SiO}_3]_0^2} \quad \dots \quad (9)$$

or, a plot of $\sqrt{t}$ against $[\text{EtOH}]/[\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ will be linear. The intercept of the line will determine

$$\frac{1}{4\sqrt{k} [\text{H}_2\text{SiO}_3]_0} \quad \text{and the slope } \frac{k_2}{4\sqrt{k} [\text{H}_2\text{SiO}_3]_0 k_1}.$$

The same explanation is applicable to the case of glycol. The values of k and k_2/k_1 as obtained from the intercepts and the slopes are summarised in Table I.

TABLE I

Medium.	Conc. of H ₂ SiO ₃ .	Temp.	k .	k_2/k_1 .
Alcohol + water	0.3298 M	55°	0.005745	7.50
Alcohol + water	0.5763	34°	0.002130	8.12
Glycol + water	0.3298	55°	0.005745	5.55

In conclusion, it may be mentioned that although Hurd and Carver⁶ found retardation of gel formation by organic solvents and obtained a linear plot between setting time and concentration of organic solvents, they did not attempt any qualitative or quantitative explanation of their observation.

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